

ACCOUNTING FOR DIGITAL ASSETS IN THE FINTECH ERA: EVALUATING THE VALUATION, RECOGNITION, AND DISCLOSURE CHALLENGES OF CRYPTOCURRENCIES AND NFTs

Thesis Submitted to

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By

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